

RESPONSE OF URBAN LAKES DUE TO INFORMAL URBAN SETTLEMENTS: A CASE STUDY IN RAIPUR CITY

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Abstract

It is evident that land and water, an important life supporting systems are under intense pressure due to human induced accelerating factors. Rapidly increasing population, over exploitation of resources, environmentally unsound infrastructural development and inadequate management practices are disturbing, damaging and degrading the natural resources especially the water regime. The area under study is Raipur city which is a capital city in Chhattisgarh state, faces the problem of urban growth on surface water quality issues. Once, Raipur was blessed with 154 lakes, which had either been built by nature or by human intervention. Over the years of imagery analysis, reduction in surface water body dominated by urban development has been identified. Presently only 85 lakes survived. Out of which 34 prominent lakes were chosen for water quality assessments. Two water quality indices are computed CCMEWQI (Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment) and NSFWQI (National Sanitation Foundation) for the standards of the parameters provided by the Central pollution control board, Ministry of Environment and Forests (Government of India). These investigations signify that there is no surface water body in the city whose water can directly use for drinking purpose. Results indicate that surface water bodies are free from nitrate contamination but there is an alarming condition for organic load. From the total 34 locations, 24 were failed to be on the safe limit. Due to increased urbanization that attracts population enhance pollution load. Large amount of organic content is the reason for obsoleting surface water body by the time.

Keywords: CCMEWQI, NSFWQI, land use change, urbanization, water quality index.

Introduction

The interaction of urbanization and surface water quality is considerably controlled by the city's land use structure as different types of land use labor various sources of contaminants and hazards which influence both water quality and quantity (Baier *et al.*, 2014; Baier *et al.*, 2015). Urbanization refers to a process in which an increasing proportion of an entire population lives in cities and the suburbs of cities and change of land use from agriculture to human settlements, commercial sectors and industries (Putra and Baier, 2008). The growing human population and development activities, increased human access to environmental resources and the exploitation of renewable or non-renewable resources of land and has led to changes in water quality (Ghorbani *et al.*, 2014). The issue of surface water contamination of wastewater disposal is an intense problem in cities of developing countries where, generally, dense populated and unsewered areas created by high rates of

migration into cities. These areas are unplanned and located in the outskirts of the cities forming shanty towns (typically between 30 and 60 percent of the overall urban population) where pit latrines or septic tanks are common. In some cities, septic tanks and pit latrines are the only way to dispose of sewage (Putra and Baier, 2008). The consumption of these different contaminants through biodegradation or toxicity resistance to these pollutants by the microbial communities can provide information about pollutant exposure, metabolic diversity and the potential source of contamination and the potential for the ecosystem natural attenuation, thus may be a practical indicator of the water quality (Karbassi *et al.*, 2011). Water quality index was first introduced in 1848 about 168 years ago in Germany where the presence or absence of certain organism in water was used as fitness indicator of a water source. The use of numerical scale to represent gradation in water quality levels is a recent phenomenon, beginning with Horton index in 1965 (Mustapha and Aris, 2011). The concept also aims at eliminating the subjective assessment of water quality and the individual biases of water resource managers (Sarkar and Abbasi, 2006). Water quality is the function of anything and everything the water might have picked up during its journey to the water body in dissolved, colloidal and suspended form. Water quality may be assessed in terms of: Quality for life (e.g., the quality of water needed for human consumption), Quality for food (e.g., the quality of water needed to sustain agricultural activities), Quality for nature (e.g., the quality of water needed to support a thriving and diverse fauna and flora in a region) and the selection of parameters used to assess the quality of water depends largely on the intended use of the body of water (Poonam *et al.*, 2013; Nikoo *et al.*, 2011).

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

The area under this study is focused on Raipur city in India. This city is located between 21°12'N to 21°18'N latitude and 81°33' to 81°41'E longitude. The whole of Raipur city is part of the open Chhattisgarh plain, which is thickly populated and closely cultivated. The climate of the study area is sub-tropical with three distinct seasons. Temperatures remain moderate for most of the year. May is the hottest month and December is the coldest. Area has hydrogeological formations comprising mainly of either limestone or sandstone/shale layer in different parts. The city experiences the average annual rainfall of 1200 mm. The Kharun River flows to the west of the city of Raipur, which is also a source of domestic water supply to the city (RMC, 2010; Sinha *et al.*, 2016). The city has a population of 11,46,383 and experienced a growth rate of 51.06% during decade 2001-2011. Present study is focused on the lakes existing in the municipal boundaries of Raipur City, Chhattisgarh, India.

The sanitation ratings conducted as per national urban sanitation policy, Raipur ranked 274 out of 423 cities with a score of 30.8/100 and falls in the red category. Raipur was blessed with 154 Talabs, which had either been built by nature or by human intervention, has presently only 85 Talabs survived. These 85 surface water bodies of varying sizes (2800 - 402000 sq.m) occupying a total surface area of 2.83 sq.km, which is about 2% of the city's area. 34 prominent Talabs were chosen for water quality assessments in this study (GIZ *et al.*, 2010; GIZ *et al.*, 2011; RMC, 2011).

Selection of Water Quality Parameters

Water quality parameters were selected to identify the most affected parameter due to pollution load on the water body. These parameters were selected on the basis of their:

- How strong is the influence of urban area on the parameter?
- Do the data values show anomalies as compared to expected values in ponds?

Figure 1. Location map of the study area

Figure 2. Population growth of Raipur city, modified after (Census-of-India, 2011; RMC, 2010)

-Pollution intimation property for the different types of uses of water body. General information, environmental effects and the different point and non-point sources for the selected water quality parameters are evaluated in present work.

DO: This constituent is measured to assess the health of the surface water body. Decreased DO level is indication of too many bacteria and an excess amount of BOD which use up DO. This reduction may be due to fertilizer runoff from farm fields and lawns.

BOD: BOD is defined as the amount of oxygen required by bacteria to decompose organic matter for 5 days under aerobic conditions. Domestic pet excreta, dumping untreated sewage sludge or discharging treated water, organic laden effluent from paper and pulp industry contribute.

EC: EC estimates the amount of total dissolved ions in the water. EC is controlled by the chemistry of the watershed soil and ultimately the lake, wastewater from septic systems, drain field on-site wastewater treatment, disposal systems and urban runoff from roads.

pH: The pH of water determines the solubility and biological availability of chemical constituents such as nutrients and heavy metals. Pollution can change water's pH, which in turn can harm animals and plants living in the water.

SAR: Salinity and SAR, must be considered together for evaluation of the ultimate effect on water infiltration rate. Other related problems such as soil crusting, poor seedling emergence, lack of aeration, plant and root diseases, weed and mosquito control problems caused by the low rate of infiltration may further complicate crop management.

Total Coliforms: All members of the total coliform group can occur in human feces, but some can also be present in animal manure, soil and submerged wood and in other places outside the human body. Their presence indicates contamination of a water supply by an outside source.

Temperature: If the overall water body temperature of a system is altered, an aquatic community shift can be expected. Water temperature is affected by air temperature, stormwater runoff, groundwater inflows, turbidity, and exposure to sunlight.

Phosphate: This may cause a change in the types of plants which live in an ecosystem. Sources of phosphate include animal wastes, sewage, detergent, fertilizer, disturbed land, and road salts used in the winter.

Turbidity: The series of turbidity-induced changes that can occur in a water body may change the composition of an aquatic community. Excess turbidity leads to fewer photosynthetic organisms available to serve as food sources for many invertebrates. As a result, overall invertebrate numbers may also decline, which may then lead to a fish population decline.

Sample collection and analysis method

Surface water samples were collected in the second week of every three months gap from July 2014 to April 2015 at three different sites from each lake like inlet, middle point and outlet. The water samples were analyzed to study the physico-chemical parameters by following the standard methods of APHA (2005). The physical parameters were examined at the spot, and chemical parameters like dissolved oxygen were also carried out near the spot. Other chemical parameters like Biochemical oxygen demand, Nitrate, Phosphate, Total hardness were analyzed at the laboratory. The pH and Dissolved Oxygen of water samples were measured immediately after sampling at the field itself. Samples were subjected to filtration before chemical analysis. The determination of TDS was done by gravimetric process while the total hardness was carried out by EDTA complex metric titration method APHA (2005). The Winkler's alkali iodide-azide method was followed for the estimation of DO and BOD. Nitrate was determined colorimetric procedure APHA (2005). Fecal coliform population was analyzed by MPN /100 ml method by growing on M-FC medium at temperature 44.5 °C and counted after 48 hr.

National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index

Brown *et al.* (1970) developed a water quality index paying great rigor in selecting parameters, developing a common scale, and assigning weights for which elaborate Delphi exercises were performed. This effort was supported by the National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) and that is why also referred as NSFQI (Bharti and Katyal, 2011). The result of nine

parameters tests used to calculate the index value of a water body to define its health. The field data is transformed into Q-value which is nothing but the rating curve or sub-indices. Sub-indices transform to non-dimensional scale values from the variables of its different units. And weighting factor sets the relative importance of a particular parameter to overall water quality.

Table 1. Standard weight system of NSFQI parameters

S.No.	Parameters	Weighting factors
1	DO	0.17
2	Fecal coliform	0.16
3	pH	0.11
4	BOD	0.11
5	Nitrate	0.1
6	Phosphate	0.1
7	Temperature	0.1
8	Turbidity	0.08
9	Total dissolved solids	0.07

The standard formula to calculate water quality index is:

$$WQI = W_{BOD}Q_{BOD} + W_{DO}Q_{DO} + W_{PH}Q_{PH} + W_{PHOSPHATE}Q_{PHOSPHATE} + W_{NITRATE}Q_{NITRATE} + W_{FC}Q_{FC} + W_{TDS}Q_{TDS} + W_{TEMP.}Q_{TEMP.} + W_{TURBIDITY}Q_{TURBIDITY}$$

where,

W_x = weight factors of the water quality parameters

Q_x = Q- value of the water quality parameters

X = water quality parameters

Based upon the weight factor and Q-values the water quality rankings for a specific pond by National Sanitation Foundation Water Quality Index are:

Index ranges	Water quality designation
0-25	Very bad
26-50	Bad
51-70	Medium
71-90	Good
91-100	Excellent

Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water quality Index

A water quality index has developed by the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME). Water quality parameters (e.g., DO, BOD, pH, Total Coli, EC) are compared to water quality guidelines or site-specific objectives. The index is based on three attributes of water quality that relate to water quality objectives:

Scope- How many? The number of water quality variables that do not meet objectives in at least one sample during the time period under consideration, relative to the total number of variables measured. *Frequency*- How often? The number of individual measurements that do

not meet objectives, relative to the total number of measurements made in all samples for the time period of interest.

Amplitude- How much? The amount by which measurements which do not meet the objectives depart from those objectives.

$$CCMEWQI = 100 - [(F_1^2 + F_2^2 + F_3^2)/1.732]^{1/2}$$

where,

F₁ represents Scope: The percentage of variables above the guideline

F₁= [No. of variables whose objectives are not met /Total no of variables]*100;

F₂ represents Frequency: The frequency by which the objectives are not met

F₂= [No of tests whose objectives are not met /Total no of tests]*100;

F₃ represents Amplitude: The range to which the failed tests are above the guideline

(a) Range/Excursion = [Failed test value/Objective]-1

(b) nse = $\sum_{i=1}^n E_j$ /No of tests

(c) F₃= [nse/0.01nse+0.01]

The constant, 1.732, is a scaling factor (square root of three) to ensure the index varies between 0 and 100. The result is further simplified by assigning it to a descriptive category.

Table 3.Categorical Description of CWQI

Category	CWQI value	Description
Excellent	95-100	Water quality is protected with a virtual absence of threat or impairment; conditions very close to natural or pristine levels. These index values can only be obtained if all measurements are within objectives virtually all of the time.
Good	80-94	Water quality is protected with only a minor degree of threat or impairment; conditions rarely depart from natural or desirable levels.
Fair	65-79	Water quality is usually protected but occasionally threatened or impaired; conditions sometimes depart from natural or desirable levels.
Marginal	45-64	Water quality is frequently threatened or impaired; conditions often depart from natural or desirable levels.
Poor	0-44	Water quality is almost always threatened or impaired; conditions usually depart from natural or desirable levels.

Results & Discussion

The pollution load on the surface water bodies has been analyzed by calculating two above stated water quality indices. To protect the surface water body by degradation and maintain its respective uses water quality index calculated for the standards of the parameters provided by the Central pollution control board, Ministry of Environment and Forests (Govt. of India). There are many water quality parameters that indicate the pollution by their aberrant concentration. According to the computation of NSFQI the table 5 reveals the present condition of the water body in Raipur city. By observing the data it is found that according to BIS (ISO: 10500) desirable limits of drinking water for the parameters chosen in NSFQI computation deviate from its standard. In any of the 34 locations turbidity and fecal coliform does not meet the drinking water quality standard. Also there are some locations at which pH, DO, BOD, Total phosphate and TDS violates the objective. It is revealed that only the Nitrate

Nitrogen is in under desirable limit of 45 mg/l. The collective effect of these parameters by the NSFQI computation represents that 5 water bodies (W12L02, W14L01, W62L03, W65L03, W65L04, W68L01) are in BAD condition and only 1 water body (W16L04) is in GOOD condition. The remaining 28 water bodies are in MEDIUM condition. Hence there is no surface water body in the Raipur city whose water can directly use for the drinking purpose.

Table 4. NSFQI Categorization of Water body

No.	LAKE_ID	LAKE_NAME	NSFWQI	Category
1	W02L06	GaonDabariTalab	69.40	MEDIUM
2	W03L01	GogaonTalab	62.34	MEDIUM
3	W04L03	GondwaraTalab	50.29	MEDIUM
4	W04L05	Bandhwa Talab-1	56.20	MEDIUM
5	W07L01	PankhatiaTalab (SHITALA TALAB)	68.19	MEDIUM
6	W07L02	KhamtaraiTalab	68.42	MEDIUM
7	W12L02	MahaniTalab	47.99	BAD
8	W14L01	DumarTalab	42.88	BAD
9	W15L02	Karbala Pond	52.33	MEDIUM
10	W16L02	DhobinTalab	55.39	MEDIUM
11	W16L03	Amma Pond	61.39	MEDIUM
12	W16L04	GhorahiTalab	71.27	GOOD
13	W24L01	Raja Talab	65.90	MEDIUM
14	W25L02	PandariTahariTalab	51.12	MEDIUM
15	W26L12	MadhiyaTalab	64.01	MEDIUM
16	W38L02	HandiTalab (Old)	57.55	MEDIUM
17	W42L01	KatoraTalab	54.34	MEDIUM
18	W43L01	Telibandha	63.55	MEDIUM
19	W49L03	Naraiya Talab-2	53.10	MEDIUM
20	W49L04	ChhiuyaTalab	53.73	MEDIUM
21	W54L01	Sarjubandha	57.23	MEDIUM
22	W56L01	ChironjiTalab	53.45	MEDIUM
23	W57L01	BudhaTalab	53.06	MEDIUM
24	W58L01	KankaliTalab	55.90	MEDIUM
25	W62L03	Maharaja ban Talab	49.87	BAD
26	W64L04	MalshayTalab	50.64	MEDIUM
27	W65L03	KhokhoTalab	41.08	BAD
28	W65L04	BandhwaTalab	49.53	BAD
29	W66L01	PahariTalab	54.58	MEDIUM
30	W68L01	Sitala Mata MandirTalab	48.06	BAD
31	W68L04	Pankhatia	61.23	MEDIUM
32	W69L01	RohinpuramTalab	63.79	MEDIUM
33	W69L02	DanganiyaTalab	61.23	MEDIUM
34	W70L01	SaronaTalab	56.23	MEDIUM

Table 5. Correlation matrix of all water quality parameters

	pH	EC	TDS	Turb	Na	Ca	Mg	NO3	T.Ph.	DO	BOD	Tcoli	Fcoli	SAR	ΔT	NSFWQI
pH	1.00															
EC	-0.40	1.00														
TDS	-0.24	0.87	1.00													
Turb	0.06	0.15	0.15	1.00												
Na	-0.22	0.89	0.82	0.20	1.00											
Ca	-0.33	0.16	0.27	-0.03	-0.12	1.00										
Mg	-0.02	0.03	0.29	-0.35	0.02	0.47	1.00									
NO3	0.24	-0.28	-0.17	0.02	-0.30	0.18	0.15	1.00								
T.Ph.	-0.52	0.39	0.34	0.07	0.17	0.55	0.15	0.30	1.00							
DO	0.16	0.06	0.08	0.04	0.12	-0.24	-0.01	0.09	0.09	1.00						
BOD	0.41	-0.13	0.16	-0.04	-0.05	0.41	0.52	0.25	0.06	-0.15	1.00					
Tcoli	-0.01	0.14	0.12	0.31	0.22	-0.19	-0.05	0.04	0.12	0.13	-0.09	1.00				
Fcoli	0.02	0.15	0.12	0.31	0.21	-0.22	-0.11	-0.09	0.05	0.14	-0.10	0.94	1.00			
SAR	-0.09	0.81	0.74	0.22	0.97	-0.30	-0.09	-0.28	0.06	0.14	-0.06	0.24	0.24	1.00		
ΔT	0.27	-0.12	-0.16	0.10	-0.18	-0.04	0.14	0.05	-0.04	-0.04	0.11	0.25	0.17	-0.16	1.00	
NSFWQI	-0.08	-0.09	-0.18	-0.40	-0.10	-0.25	-0.11	-0.35	-0.28	0.56	-0.51	-0.30	-0.23	-0.09	-0.23	1.00

Figure 3.Box Plots of all water quality parameters used to calculate WQI

Figure 4. NSF WQI value variation for all lakes

To identify the prominent parameter that affected seriously by pollution, CCMEWQI applied location wise. Central pollution control board, Ministry of Environment and Forests (Govt. of India) guidelines are considered for maintaining the respective use without degrading its life span and quality. Table 6 depicts the CCMEWQI result.

Table 6. CCMEWQI analysis for 34 surface water bodies in study area

Parameters	pH	EC	SAR	DO	BOD	Total Coli.	NO3
Total No. of locations	34	34	34	34	34	34	34
Number of failed locations	3	1	11	16	24	5	0
Total No. of tests	136	136	136	136	136	136	136
Number of failed tests	12	4	44	64	96	20	0
F1	8.82	2.94	32.35	47.06	70.59	14.71	0
F2	8.82	2.94	32.35	47.06	70.59	14.71	0
Excursion	0.18	0.04	11.51	10.37	35.25	19.40	0
Nse	0.01	0.00	0.34	0.31	1.04	0.57	0
F3	0.54	0.10	25.29	23.38	50.90	36.33	0
CWQI	92.79	97.60	69.82	59.27	35.30	66.27	100
Category	Good	Excellent	Fair	Marginal	Poor	Fair	Excellent

From the above table 6 BOD is that parameter which is particularly more affected by the urban pollution in most of the Raipur cities surface water body. It categorized under poor condition according to CCMEWQI criteria. DO is marginal and SAR & Total Coli is in fair condition. Table 7 displays the water body ID's that violates the standard.

Table 6. Water body ID's violates standard

No.	pH	EC	SAR	DO	BOD	Total Coli
1	W02L06	W16L03	W03L01	W04L03	W02L06	W03L01
2	W14L01		W04L05	W04L05	W03L01	W07L01
3	W69L02		W16L02	W14L01	W04L03	W56L01
4			W16L03	W15L02	W12L02	W62L03
5			W38L02	W25L02	W14L01	W65L03
6			W54L01	W26L12	W15L02	
7			W56L01	W42L01	W16L02	
8			W64L04	W43L01	W16L03	
9			W65L03	W49L04	W25L02	
10			W68L01	W57L01	W38L02	
11			W68L04	W58L01	W42L01	
12				W65L04	W49L03	
13				W68L01	W49L04	
14				W68L04	W54L01	
15				W69L01	W57L01	

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16				W70L01	W58L01	
17					W62L03	
18					W64L04	
19					W65L03	
20					W65L04	
21					W66L01	
22					W68L01	
23					W69L01	
24					W69L02	

It is observed from the above table 7 that there are 24 water bodies in which BOD violates the standard of pollution control board. After that DO and SAR violates the standard at 16 and 11 locations respectively. Total Coli, pH and EC are violates standard at 5, 3 and 1 location respectively. Above table depicts that the organic load is more on the surface water body of the Raipur city, which could be due to inadequate and deficiently designed, operated and managed individual and community toilets in the urban poor areas resulting in open defecation. This leads to pollution and sever health impacts. The sewage management system is deficient in city of Raipur which is evident from the fact that roughly 54% of the properties are connected to unscientifically designed septic tanks, part of which overflows into the open drains/areas ultimately draining into the natural water bodies.

Conclusion

The contradictory research findings in relation to these measures clearly point to the significant role played by location specific factors influencing water quality rather than purely land use. The underlying processes and concepts relating to urban water quality are well known in a qualitative sense. However their quantification has proved to be extremely difficult. Chemical processes exert a strong influence on urban storm water quality characteristics. Rainfall and the resulting surface runoff transports a variety of materials of chemical and biological origin to the nearest receiving water body. This results in a water body which is fundamentally changed from its natural state. Urban expansion transforms local environments and can dramatically alter local conditions and in particular the rate of movement of pollutants into waterways, thereby adversely changing the quality of water. The concentration of contaminants in the atmosphere is influenced by meteorological, topographical and land use factors. The chemical composition and concentration patterns of atmospheric pollution can vary widely, either temporally or spatially due to meteorological factors which will result in processes such as dispersion and re-suspension. These processes do not lend themselves to simple mathematical modeling. Common substances include carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons and dust. They are brought into the urban atmosphere from long distances or could be emitted from various sources either on a regional or local scale. The primary sources include lawn fertilizer, sewer overflows, animal waste, vegetation debris, industrial activities, vehicle exhausts, power generation and atmospheric dry and wet deposition. Some of the atmospheric pollutants in the solute or gaseous phases will undergo further synthesis due to physical, chemical or photochemical processes.

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